

Kindergarten Teachers' Strategies for Enhancing Literacy Competence in Preparation for Grade 1: Basis for an Instructional Support Framework

Jocelyn G. Vidal¹, Maria Lourdes Lao-Namocot, PhD²

^{1,2} Pacific InterContinental College, Las Piñas, Metro Manila, Philippines

EMAIL: jocelyngalimba17@gmail.com¹, desslao5570@gmail.com²

Received: 21.03.2026 | Accepted: 24.04.2026 | Published: 25.05.2026

DOI: 10.5281/zenodo.20430326

ABSTRACT

RESEARCH ARTICLE

This study explored kindergarten teachers' literacy instruction practices and their influence on learners' readiness for Grade 1, focusing on instructional strategies, lived experiences and challenges, perceptions of readiness, and needed support systems. Grounded in Emergent Literacy Theory, Vygotsky's Sociocultural Theory, and Bronfenbrenner's Ecological Systems Theory, the research employed a qualitative design using Interpretative Phenomenological Analysis (IPA) with seven purposively selected kindergarten teachers. Data were collected through in-depth, semi-structured interviews and analyzed through systematic coding and thematic development. Findings revealed that teachers adopt a balanced and integrative approach, combining phonics-based instruction with play-based and interactive activities such as sound blending, storytelling, guided writing, and the use of songs, rhymes, and games, alongside structured tools like Alpabasa. Teachers also emphasized the importance of print-rich and language-rich environments to support continuous literacy exposure. However, challenges such as diverse learner abilities, limited resources, large class sizes, and short attention spans were reported. Grade 1 readiness was perceived as multidimensional, encompassing both foundational literacy skills and behavioral competencies. Assessment practices were largely authentic and observation-based, aligning with early childhood principles. The study further highlighted the importance of professional development, instructional resources, institutional support, and parental involvement, noting disparities in home literacy environments. Based on these findings, the study proposes an Integrated Literacy Instructional Support Framework (ILISF) that underscores teacher capacity building, strategic instruction, resource provision, authentic assessment, and strengthened home-school collaboration. Overall, the study contributes to early childhood education by emphasizing the need for holistic, context-responsive, and collaborative approaches to enhance literacy development and ensure learners' readiness for formal schooling.

KEYWORDS: Kindergarten teachers, literacy competence, early literacy development, Grade 1 readiness, instructional strategies, instructional strategies, instructional support framework, emergent literacy

INTRODUCTION

The transition from kindergarten to Grade 1 is a critical stage in a child's educational development, marked by a shift from play-based learning to formal literacy instruction. At this stage, learners are expected to progress from recognizing letters and sounds to reading, writing, and constructing simple texts. However, many children enter Grade 1 without adequate readiness due to disparities in preschool experiences, access to resources, and home literacy environments.

Kindergarten plays a crucial role in building foundational literacy skills through strategies such as phonics instruction, guided reading, storytelling, and play-based activities. These approaches support the development of phonological awareness and print knowledge, which are essential for successful transition to formal schooling. In the Philippines, policies such as Republic Act No. 10157 and Republic Act No. 10533 emphasize the importance of early literacy through developmentally appropriate and child-centered approaches. Despite these mandates, challenges such as overcrowded classrooms, limited instructional materials, and inconsistent teacher training hinder effective implementation.

Research highlights the effectiveness of play-based learning, phonemic awareness activities, and parental involvement in enhancing early literacy skills and readiness for Grade 1. However, there remains a lack of a unified and context-responsive instructional framework in the Philippine setting, resulting in varied teaching practices and uneven learner outcomes.

In response, this study proposes an instructional support framework that integrates effective literacy strategies and aligns with existing educational policies. The framework aims to support teachers in delivering coherent and responsive literacy instruction, ultimately improving learners' readiness for Grade 1 and fostering long-term academic success.

1.1 Research Objectives

This study aims to achieve the following objectives:

- To identify the literacy instruction strategies used by kindergarten teachers to develop emergent literacy among learners.
- To describe kindergarten teachers' experiences and challenges in implementing literacy instruction strategies.
- To determine kindergarten teachers' perceptions of learners' Grade 1 readiness in terms of literacy competence.
- To determine the forms of support needed by kindergarten teachers to strengthen literacy instruction and promote Grade 1 readiness.
- To propose an Instructional Support Framework based on the findings of the study.

1.2 Research Gap

A strong body of literature highlights effective literacy instruction strategies for developing early reading skills and preparing learners for Grade 1. Local studies emphasize the effectiveness of the Marungko Approach (Nabua et al., 2025; Canaveral et al., 2023), play-based and multimodal strategies (Sibulo, 2025; Liwag & Marquez, 2025), parental involvement (Badidoy & Tapac, 2025; Jomboy, 2025), and technology integration (De Vera & Casingal, 2025). International studies further support guided play, digital tools, teacher

competence, and authentic assessment as key factors in early literacy development (Pyle et al., 2024; Liu et al., 2024; Cheruiyot, 2024; Quinn, 2025; Kim, 2024; Watts, 2024).

Despite these findings, existing studies generally examine these factors separately rather than as an integrated instructional system. Moreover, there remains limited qualitative research that explores how kindergarten teachers implement these strategies in real classroom contexts amid challenges such as overcrowded classes, limited resources, and varying home support. This gap highlights the need for a context-responsive instructional support framework that integrates teachers' practices and experiences to strengthen literacy instruction and improve learners' Grade 1 readiness.

2. Literature Review

A strong body of local research highlights the effectiveness of structured and contextualized literacy strategies in preparing learners for Grade 1. The Marungko Approach has been widely recognized for improving early reading skills. Nabua et al. (2025) and Canaverl et al. (2023) both reported significant gains in phonics development and reading proficiency using this method, emphasizing its role in strengthening decoding skills and reading confidence among kindergarten learners.

Beyond phonics instruction, play-based and multimodal strategies have also been shown to enhance literacy development. Sibulo (2025) found that audio-visual learning materials improve letter recognition, phonemic awareness, and reading confidence. Similarly, Liwag and Marquez (2025) demonstrated that play-based learning strategies such as storytelling, role-playing, and games significantly enhance vocabulary development, comprehension, and phonological awareness, making literacy learning more engaging and developmentally appropriate.

Parental involvement has also been identified as a critical factor in early literacy success. Badidoy and Tapac (2025) revealed that learners with strong home support through shared reading and literacy activities demonstrate higher phonemic awareness and word recognition compared to those with limited parental engagement. This underscores the importance of home-school collaboration in reinforcing classroom instruction.

In addition, De Vera and Casingal (2025) found that phonics-based mobile applications significantly improved learners' reading performance, demonstrating the value of integrating technology in literacy instruction. Complementing this, Jomboy (2025) confirmed that parental-supported literacy activities at home significantly enhance reading readiness, reinforcing that literacy development extends beyond the classroom.

Colina et al. (2024) further emphasized that socioeconomic and environmental factors influence reading readiness, while Lavador et al. (2024) found that parental education levels strongly predict literacy outcomes. These studies highlight the unequal starting points of learners and the need for equitable instructional support.

Furthermore, DepEd Order No. 47, s. 2016 reinforces the use of authentic and observation-based assessment in kindergarten through tools such as the ECCD checklist, portfolios, and anecdotal records. However, challenges such as large class sizes and limited resources hinder effective implementation, affecting consistent monitoring of literacy development.

International literature consistently emphasizes the effectiveness of guided play and structured instruction in early literacy development. Pyle et al. (2024) found that guided play enhances vocabulary, letter knowledge, and comprehension while maintaining learner engagement, making it a balanced approach for early childhood education.

Technology integration is also widely supported in foreign studies. Liu et al. (2024) reported that interactive storybooks and literacy apps improve phonological awareness and vocabulary acquisition. Similarly, Nevrelova et al. (2024) and Burgos and Anthony (2024) found that augmented reality tools and digital literacy practices enhance engagement, comprehension, and language development, particularly in multilingual settings.

Cheruiyot (2024) further emphasized that play-based learning across cultural contexts improves literacy outcomes, including phonemic awareness, vocabulary, and comprehension, confirming its global relevance in early childhood education.

Teacher competence and instructional quality are also critical. Quinn (2025) found that teachers' understanding of literacy development significantly influences instructional effectiveness, while Alvarez-Marinelli et al. (2023) demonstrated that professional development programs improve both teaching practices and learner literacy outcomes.

Assessment practices also play a vital role. Kim (2024) and Watts (2024) highlighted that continuous assessment of school readiness and literacy skills allows teachers to identify learning gaps and adjust instruction accordingly, ensuring better preparedness for Grade 1.

Overall, the literature reveals that early literacy development is influenced by a combination of phonics-based instruction, play-based learning, digital integration, parental involvement, teacher competence, and authentic assessment practices. While these strategies are effective individually, research consistently shows that their integration produces stronger literacy outcomes and better Grade 1 readiness.

However, despite the availability of these evidence-based practices, challenges such as overcrowded classrooms, limited resources, inconsistent teacher training, and unequal home support remain prevalent in Philippine settings. These gaps highlight the need for a structured and context-responsive Instructional Support Framework that can unify effective strategies and support teachers in delivering consistent and high-quality literacy instruction.

3. Research Methodology

This study employed a qualitative research design to explore kindergarten teachers' literacy instruction strategies and their role in supporting learners' transition to Grade 1. It focused on teachers' lived experiences to gain in-depth understanding of instructional practices, challenges, and support needs. The study involved seven purposively selected public kindergarten teachers from Tunasan Elementary School for the 2025–2026 school year, each with at least one year of teaching experience. Data were gathered through semi-structured interviews guided by open-ended questions covering literacy strategies, assessment practices, instructional challenges, and support needs. The interview guide was validated by early childhood education experts and pilot-tested for clarity and relevance before use. Data collection was conducted over two weeks through face-to-face interviews, which were audio-recorded with consent and supplemented by field notes to ensure accuracy and contextual depth. The data were analyzed using Braun and Clarke's thematic analysis, involving transcription, coding, theme development, and refinement to identify key patterns such as

instructional strategies, assessment practices, challenges, and support systems. Trustworthiness was ensured through peer debriefing, triangulation, reflexive journaling, and member checking. Ethical standards were strictly observed, including informed consent, confidentiality, anonymity, and compliance with the Data Privacy Act of 2012 (Republic Act 10173).

4. Analysis and Discussion

Table 1
Theme 1: Balanced Literacy Instruction through Phonics and Play-Based Learning

Participants' Verbatim Statements	Codes	Sub codes	Theme
R1: "I use alphabet songs, rhymes, letter hunts..." R3: "I use play-based activities like alphabet songs..." R5: "I use alphabet songs and rhyming games..." R7: "I use alphabet songs and letter matching..."	Alphabet songs	Play-based strategies	Balanced Literacy Instruction through Phonics and Play-Based Learning
R2: "I use phonemic awareness games, songs, and rhymes..." R4: "I use songs, rhymes, and activities..."	Rhyming / games	Play-based strategies	
R1: "I use sound blending..."	Sound blending	Phonics-based instruction	
R2: "I use phonics..." R6: "I use phonics instruction..."	Phonics instruction	Phonics-based instruction	
R1: "Alpabasa mapping board..." R2: "I use Alpabasa..."	Alpabasa	Structured literacy tool	
R3: "Tracing letters..." R4: "Writing simple words..." R6: "Guided writing..."	Guided writing / tracing	Early writing practices	
R5: "Flashcards and charts..."	Flashcards / charts	Instructional materials	

The findings reveal that kindergarten teachers use a balanced approach that integrates structured phonics instruction with play-based learning. Strategies such as sound blending, letter recognition, guided writing, songs, and games demonstrate how teachers combine systematic skill development with engaging, developmentally appropriate activities. This approach reflects teachers' intent to enhance both literacy competence and learner participation.

This finding supports Emergent Literacy Theory, which emphasizes learning through meaningful and interactive experiences. It also aligns with studies by Nabua et al. (2025) and Canaverl et al. (2023) on the effectiveness of phonics instruction, and Liwag and Marquez (2025) on the value of play-based strategies, confirming that a blended approach strengthens early literacy development.

Table 2
Theme 2: Multisensory and Interactive Literacy Practices

Participants' Verbatim Statements	Codes	Sub codes	Theme
R5: "I maintain a print-rich classroom..." R7: "Word walls and displays..."	Word walls / labels	Print-rich environment	Literacy as an Immersive and Interactive Experience
R3: "Reading corner..."	Reading corner	Print-rich environment	
R3: "Daily read-alouds..." R4: "I use read-aloud..." R6: "Interactive read-aloud..."	Read-aloud	Language-rich practices	
R1: "Storytelling..." R4: "Storytelling..."	Storytelling	Language-rich practices	
R3: "Interactive discussions..."	Interactive discussion	Oral language development	
R3: "Shared writing..."	Shared writing	Collaborative literacy	

The findings show that teachers use hands-on, interactive, and multisensory activities to enhance literacy learning. Strategies such as letter-sound scavenger hunts, matching games, storytelling, and read-aloud sessions actively engage learners and promote experiential learning. Teachers also create print-rich environments through word walls, reading corners, and visual labels, immersing learners in meaningful literacy experiences.

These practices reflect the view that literacy is best developed through active participation and interaction. The findings support Vygotsky's Sociocultural Theory, emphasizing the role of social interaction and environment in learning, and align with studies (Yin et al., 2023; Sibulo, 2025) highlighting the effectiveness of interactive strategies and print-rich classrooms in improving vocabulary and early reading skills.

Table 3
Theme 3: Teaching as a Rewarding yet Demanding Practice

Participants' Verbatim statements	Codes	Sub codes	Theme
R1: "It is challenging but very rewarding..." R4: "Challenging but fulfilling..."	Challenging but rewarding	Emotional experience	Teaching as a Rewarding yet Demanding Practice
R3: "I enjoy seeing children grow..." R7: "It is rewarding to see learners grow..."	Enjoy seeing learners grow	Professional fulfillment	
R5: "Helping learners build skills..." R6: "Helping learners grow academically..."	Helping learners develop	Teacher satisfaction	
R2: "Building their confidence..."	Building confidence	Learner development	

Findings show that teachers perceive literacy instruction as both challenging and fulfilling. Despite difficulties, they find satisfaction in learners' progress and development, reflecting strong professional commitment and emotional investment. Teaching is viewed as a meaningful practice that shapes their sense of purpose and identity. This aligns with Quinn (2025), highlighting how teachers' perceptions influence motivation and engagement, and underscores the emotional demands of early childhood education.

Table 4
Theme 4: Managing Learner Diversity and Engagement Challenges

Participants' Verbatim Statements	Codes	Sub codes	Theme
R1: "Mixed-ability groups..."	Mixed-ability learners	Learner diversity	Managing Learner Diversity and Engagement Challenges
R3: "Different learning levels..." R6: "Wide range of readiness..."	Different readiness levels	Learner diversity	
R2: "Short attention span..." R5: "Learners lose focus..."	Short attention span	Engagement challenges	
R3: "Struggle with letters and sounds..."	Difficulty recognizing letters	Foundational gaps	
R1: "Limited materials..." R4: "Limited resources..."	Limited materials	Resource constraints	
R4: "Large class..."	Large class size	Classroom constraints	

Findings reveal that teachers face challenges in managing diverse learner abilities, maintaining engagement, and addressing short attention spans. Differentiation is necessary but complex, requiring teachers to constantly adapt strategies. Additionally, limited instructional materials and large class sizes further constrain effective teaching, often requiring improvisation.

These findings highlight that literacy instruction is influenced by both learner diversity and contextual factors, aligning with Bronfenbrenner's Ecological Systems Theory. They are also consistent with studies (Colina et al., 2024; Lavador et al., 2024; Liwag & Marquez, 2025) emphasizing the impact of learners' backgrounds and the importance of engagement strategies in early literacy development.

Table 5
Theme 5: Readiness as Mastery of Foundational Literacy Skills

Participants' Verbatim Statements	Codes	Sub-codes	Theme
R3: "Recognize letters..." R5: "Recognizing letters..."	Letter recognition	Foundational skills	Readiness as Mastery of Foundational Literacy Skills
R1: "Recognize sounds..."	Sound recognition	Phonemic awareness	

Participants' Verbatim Statements	Codes	Sub-codes	Theme
R3: "Read simple words..."	Reading simple words	Early reading	
R1: "Write simple words..."	Writing simple words	Early writing	
R1: "Retell stories..." R6: "Story retelling..."	Story retelling	Comprehension	
R1: "Follow instructions..."	Following instructions	Behavioral readiness	

Findings show that teachers view readiness as mastery of foundational literacy skills, including letter recognition, phonemic awareness, early reading, writing, comprehension, and the ability to follow instructions. Readiness is perceived as functional competence—the ability to apply literacy skills in meaningful contexts.

Table 6
Theme 6: Observation-Based Assessment Practices

Participants' Verbatim Statements	Codes	Sub-codes	Theme
R2: "Continuous observation..."	Continuous observation	Informal assessment	
R4: "I rely on observation..."	Classroom observation	Authentic assessment	
R5: "I observe during activities..."	Daily activities	Embedded assessment	Observation-Based Assessment Practices
R7: "Quick checks..."	Quick checks	Ongoing assessment	
R6: "Guided assessment..."	Guided assessment	Informal methods	

Findings show that teachers use informal, observation-based, and continuous assessment to evaluate learners' literacy readiness through daily classroom activities such as reading, writing, and participation. Assessment is embedded in instruction rather than done through formal testing.

This aligns with DepEd and ECCD guidelines on authentic assessment and supports Watts (2024), who emphasized that ongoing assessment helps teachers adjust instruction to learner needs, reflecting a shift toward formative, learner-centered assessment practices.

Table 7
Theme 7: Need for Instructional and Professional Support

Participants' Verbatim Statements	Codes	Sub codes	Theme
R1: "Limited materials affect teaching..." R5: "Materials shape my teaching..."	Need for materials	Instructional resources	Need for Instructional and Professional Support

Participants' Verbatim Statements	Codes	Sub codes	Theme
R4: "I seek guidance to improve..."	Need for training	Professional development	
R6: "School support affects planning..."	Need for support	Institutional support	
R3: "Curriculum influences teaching..."	Curriculum support	Instructional guidance	

Findings show that teachers need continuous training, guidance, and adequate instructional materials to improve literacy instruction. They emphasized that professional development and resource availability directly affect teaching effectiveness and learner outcomes.

This supports Álvarez-Marinelli et al. (2023) and Lavador et al. (2024), highlighting that effective literacy instruction depends on both teacher development and system-level support.

Table 8
Theme 8: Importance of Home–School Partnership

Participants' Verbatim Statements	Codes	Sub-codes	Theme
R1: "Families who read..."			
R5: "Parents read with children..."	Reading at home	Home literacy practices	
R3: "Practice letters and sounds..."	Practice at home	Reinforcement	
R6: "Parents reinforce learning..."	Parent support	Motivation	Importance of Home–School Partnership
R7: "Families communicate with teachers..."	Communication	Collaboration	
R4: "Not all families support..."	Inconsistent support	Barriers	

Findings show that parental involvement supports learners' literacy development by improving motivation, confidence, and reading skills, while inconsistent support remains a challenge. This highlights literacy development as a shared responsibility between home and school.

This aligns with Badidoy and Tapac (2025) and Jomboy (2025), who emphasized the positive impact of home literacy practices on reading readiness, while also reflecting how socioeconomic factors influence learner outcomes within an ecological perspective.

Table 9
Proposed Instructional Support Framework

Component	Objective	Strategies/Activities	Persons Involved	Expected Outcomes
1. Teacher Capacity	Enhance teachers'	• Training on phonics and play-based	Teachers, School Heads,	Improved instructional

Component	Objective	Strategies/Activities	Persons Involved	Expected Outcomes
Building	knowledge and skills in literacy instruction	and strategies • Workshops on differentiated instruction • Peer mentoring and coaching • Integration of phonics and play-based learning	Trainers	competence and confidence
2. Instructional Strategies Enhancement	Strengthen the implementation of effective literacy practices	• Multisensory and interactive activities • Use of print-rich environment • Development of literacy kits (flashcards, charts, storybooks)	Teachers	Increased learner engagement and literacy development
3. Provision of Instructional Resources	Ensure availability of teaching materials	• Use of localized and contextualized materials • Observation-based assessment	School Administrators, Teachers	Improved teaching effectiveness and learner participation
4. Assessment and Monitoring	Promote continuous and authentic assessment	• Use of performance tasks • Regular progress monitoring • Parent orientation programs	Teachers	Accurate tracking of learners' literacy development
5. Home–School Partnership	Strengthen parental involvement in literacy	• Home reading activities • Communication through progress reports • Allocation of resources	Teachers, Parents	Enhanced literacy reinforcement at home
6. Institutional Support System	Provide administrative and policy support	• Monitoring and supervision • Policy support for literacy programs	School Heads, Administrators	Sustained implementation of literacy programs

The proposed framework is a context-responsive, multi-dimensional model designed to strengthen kindergarten literacy instruction by addressing instructional strategies, teacher capacity, learning resources, assessment practices, and home–school collaboration. Grounded on the view that literacy development is holistic and collaborative, it involves coordinated support from teachers, schools, and families. The framework includes teacher training, improved instructional strategies, provision of learning resources, authentic assessment,

parental engagement, and institutional support. It follows a structured implementation process (preparation, capacity building, implementation, monitoring, and enhancement) and is supported by a monitoring and evaluation system to ensure continuous improvement in teacher performance, learner literacy development, classroom engagement, and program effectiveness.

5. Research Future Opportunities

While this study provides valuable insights into kindergarten teachers' literacy instruction strategies and their role in supporting learners' Grade 1 readiness, several areas warrant further investigation:

- **Longitudinal Studies on Literacy Instruction Practices:** Future research may explore how kindergarten teachers' literacy instruction strategies evolve over time and how these practices continuously influence learners' literacy development and Grade 1 readiness.
- **Evaluation of the Proposed Instructional Support Framework:** Further studies may examine the implementation and effectiveness of the proposed Instructional Support Framework in improving teachers' instructional practices and learners' literacy outcomes in actual classroom settings.
- **Impact of Teacher Professional Development:** Future research may investigate the specific effects of training programs on phonics instruction, play-based learning, and assessment practices in enhancing teachers' literacy teaching competence.
- **Home-School Collaboration in Literacy Development:** Additional studies may focus on the extent and quality of parental involvement and how home literacy practices contribute to learners' reading readiness and academic success.
- **Contextual Factors Affecting Literacy Instruction:** Further research may explore how classroom conditions such as class size, resource availability, and institutional support influence the implementation of effective literacy instruction in public kindergarten schools.

6. Conclusion

The study concludes that kindergarten literacy instruction is most effective when it integrates phonics-based and play-based strategies, promoting both skill development and learner engagement. Literacy is further strengthened through print-rich and language-rich classroom environments that provide continuous exposure to reading and writing. Although teachers face challenges such as diverse learner needs and resource constraints, they remain committed and adaptive in their instructional practices. Grade 1 readiness is understood as a holistic construct that includes foundational literacy skills, comprehension, communication, and behavioral readiness. Assessment is most effective when it is authentic, continuous, and embedded in daily classroom activities. Overall, effective literacy development requires collaborative and systemic support involving teachers, school leaders, parents, and adequate instructional resources.

Acknowledgment: The researcher sincerely expresses her gratitude to all who contributed to the successful completion of this study. She is deeply thankful to Almighty God for His guidance, wisdom, strength, and blessings throughout the research process. She extends heartfelt appreciation to her thesis adviser for her expert guidance, patience, and continuous support, as well as to the panel members for their valuable insights and recommendations that

improved the study. She likewise acknowledges the school principal and master teacher for their assistance in validating the research instrument and supporting the conduct of the study. The researcher is also grateful to the kindergarten teacher participants for their cooperation and willingness to share their experiences. Finally, she expresses her deepest appreciation to her family for their unconditional love, encouragement, and support, and to all individuals who contributed directly or indirectly to the completion of this study.

Data Availability Statement: The datasets generated and analyzed during this study are available from the corresponding author upon reasonable request.

Funding Statement: This study did not receive any specific grant or financial support.

Conflicts of Interest Statement: The authors declare that there are no financial, personal, or professional conflicts of interest that could have influenced the research, its findings, or the content of this manuscript.

Ethics and Consent Statement: This study was conducted in accordance with ethical standards to ensure respondents' privacy, confidentiality, and security. Informed consent was obtained after clearly explaining the study's objectives and procedures, in compliance with Republic Act 10173 – Data Privacy Act of 2012. All data were anonymized, participation was voluntary, and interviews were conducted in private. Any future data sharing will adhere to ethical guidelines and require explicit consent from respondents.

References

1. Álvarez-Marínelli, H., Berlinski, S., Busso, M., & Martínez-Correa, J. (2023). Improving early literacy through teacher professional development: Experimental evidence from Colombia. *Journal of Public Economics Plus*, 4, 100019. <https://doi.org/10.1016/j.pubecp.2023.100019>
2. Badidoy, L., & Tapac, J. (2025). Role of parental involvement in enhancing early literacy skills among kindergarten learners. *EPRA International Journal of Multidisciplinary Research*, 11(5). <https://eprajournals.com/IJMR/article/14819>
3. Burgos, M. V., & Anthony, J. E. S. (2024). Digital literacy and language learning: The role of information technology in enhancing English proficiency. *American Journal of Education and Technology*.
4. Canaveral, D., Quino, C., Opingo, K. M., Fulgencio, M., Plando, D., Revalde, H., & Padillo, G. (2023). Effects of the Marungko approach on the reading competencies of beginning readers. *World Journal on Education and Humanities Research*, 3(4), 254–264. <https://wjehr.com/home/article/view/166>
5. Cheruiyot, B. (2024). Effectiveness of a play-based learning method in promoting early literacy skills among ECDE children. *East African Journal of Education Studies*, 7(3), 479–488. <https://doi.org/10.37284/eajes.7.3.2178>
6. Colina, E., Santos, R., & Villanueva, L. (2024). Reading readiness of young learners in Adlaon Integrated School SY 2023–2024. *ResearchGate*. https://www.researchgate.net/publication/378137888_Reading_Readiness_of_Young_Learners_in_Adlaon_Integrated_School_SY_2023-2024

7. De Vera, R., & Casingal, R. (2025). Mobile application for developing reading skills among kindergarten learners. *SAJAAS*. <https://sajaas.basc.edu.ph/index.php/sajaas/article/view/24>
8. Jomboy, P. C. (2025). Parent-assisted early literacy and numeracy practices: Basis for a proposed intervention program. *Randwick International of Education and Linguistics Science Journal*, 6(2), 385–399. <https://www.randwickresearch.com/index.php/rielsj/article/view/1197>
9. Kim, J. (2024). The relationships between teachers' evaluation of children's academic readiness and children's later outcomes. *International Journal of Child Care and Education Policy*, 18, Article 6. <https://doi.org/10.1186/s40723-024-00131-0>
10. Liu, S., Reynolds, B. L., Thomas, N., & Soyoo, A. (2024). The use of digital technologies to develop young children's language and literacy skills: A systematic review. *SAGE Open*, 14(3), 1–14. <https://doi.org/10.1177/21582440241230850>
11. Liwag, B. S. E., & Marquez, M. F. (2025). The impact of play-based learning on literacy skills of kindergarten learners. *EPRA International Journal of Multidisciplinary Research*, 11(7), 55–62. <https://doi.org/10.36713/epra23303>
12. Nabua, J., Opingo, K. M., Duites, A., Mangubat, R., & Calasang, V. (2025). Advancing early literacy through the impact of the Marungko approach on kindergarten reading proficiency. *International Journal of Social Sciences and English Literature*, 9(2), 1–6. <https://doi.org/10.55220/2576683x.v9.266>
13. Pyle, A., Wickstrom, H., Gross, O., & Kraszewski, M. (2024). Supporting literacy development in kindergarten through teacher-facilitated play. *Journal of Early Childhood Literacy*, 24(2), 215–233. <https://doi.org/10.1177/1476718X231221363>
14. Quinn, K. (2025). Understanding preschool educators' writing knowledge: Insights from the Early Writing Knowledge Assessment. *Reading Research Quarterly*. <https://doi.org/10.1002/rrq.589>
15. Sibulo, C. N. (2025). Audio-visual supplementary materials in developing the reading readiness of kindergarten learners. *International Journal on Science and Technology*, 16(2), Article 3511. <https://doi.org/10.71097/IJSAT.v16.i2.3511>
16. Watts, C. T. (2024). Kindergarten teachers' perspectives about literacy and the relevance of assessments: Impact on students' success and first grade transition (Doctoral dissertation). St. John's University.
17. Yin, H., Cheung, A. C. K., Tam, W. W. Y., & Lau, E. (2023). Facilitating Hong Kong kindergarten teachers' perceptions of enactment of play-based learning for whole-child development: The potential of personal and organizational enablers. *Early Education and Development*, 34(6), 1063–1082. <https://doi.org/10.1080/10409289.2023.2298643>